

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-10

Active atmospheric
water condensation for
greenhouse water recovery
and microclimate control

//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Active atmospheric water condensation system via cold surface cooled by heat pump

INPUTS

Greenhouse Humidity; collection surfaces

OUTPUTS

Recovered condensate water for reuse for nursery irrigation, technical or domestic uses

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 6

CONTEXT & SCALE

Greenhouse-based application at small-scale plant nursery level (glasshouse seedling production)

KEY BENEFITS

Recovery of an internal freshwater source; reduction of excess greenhouse humidity; improved plant health and reduced fungal risk

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Low water volumes recovered (in the order of tens of liters); dependence on air humidity and electricity supply for active condensation

CATEGORY

Atmospheric water condensation

//02. WHAT IT IS

The active atmospheric water condensation system is based on an industrial dehumidifier that is optimized for greenhouse conditions. It is a technical solution installed inside a greenhouse to recover water from humid air while simultaneously supporting microclimate control. It condenses water vapour generated by plant

transpiration into distilled water that can be reused on-site.

By removing excess humidity caused by plant transpiration, the system reduces leaf wetness and fungal disease risk, while producing small volumes of high-quality distilled water for reuse in nursery operations, technical or domestic uses.

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//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In greenhouse-based seedling production, excess air humidity and leaf wetness can increase the risk of fungal diseases and negatively affect plant health. This risk is further amplified when nature-based wastewater treatment and reuse systems are integrated into enclosed cultivation spaces and contribute additional moisture through plant transpiration.

By actively removing excess humidity and recovering water from the greenhouse air, the system supports stable microclimatic conditions while providing a small but reliable internal source of high-quality water. This contributes to improved production conditions and increases water use efficiency.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

The design is based on an industrial dehumidifier. The design criteria include greenhouse volume, expected plant evapotranspiration, and diurnal/seasonal temperature variability. For maximum efficiency, inlet and outlet locations are optimised to capture air with the highest dew point and to

enable beneficial use of exhaust air for microclimate control (e.g.: using warm exhaust air for heating in autumn). Depending on the configuration and conditions, this way around 15-30 liters of water can be recovered per day.

Schematic illustration of an active atmospheric water condensation unit for greenhouse water recovery and micro climate control © ANRI 2025

//05. HOW IT WORKS

Condensation forms on a surface actively cooled by a heat pump. The system condenses the water vapor from humid greenhouse air (by plant transpiration) by guiding it onto that cooled surface, converting it

into distilled water. The recovered water is collected in a small buffer tank and reused within the glasshouse, mainly for nursery operations such as seedling irrigation.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

The active atmospheric water condensation system operates automatically inside the greenhouse during the growing season. Routine operation is integrated into normal greenhouse management and nursery activities.

Regular visual checks are required to ensure proper system functioning, including verification of air humidity reduction, water collection, and storage conditions. The recovered distilled water is reused directly within the glasshouse.

The in- and outlet airflow is adjusted twice a year to reflect seasonal conditions.. In the cold season, the warm outlet air will be used to warm the greenhouse. In the warmer seasons it will be discharged to the outside thereby promoting inflow of cooler surrounding air.

Heat-pump maintenance is carried out by specialised service providers.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

Inlets and outlets should be checked regularly for leaves, cobwebs, and other debris that may obstruct airflow. The condensation panel needs to be inspected for dirt or mould formation, which can adversely affect the quality of the produced water.

The generated water must be evaluated to ensure it is suitable for the intended pur-

pose. While no additional testing is required for irrigation use, regular quality monitoring is necessary if the water is intended to replace distilled water in technical equipment , and extra hygiene control (filtration/ disinfection) if it is to be converted into drinking water.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Greenhouse-based seedling production systems. The system is particularly suited for sites where excess air humidity occurs due to intensive plant production, where there is green wall integration, high temperature fluctuations, and where small volumes of high-quality water can be reused internally.

Within the GEORGIA project, this solution is implemented in a [regenerative market garden and plant nursery pilot in southeastern Austria](#) , combined with a vertECO® vertical wastewater treatment green wall (FS2.1-01).

//09. KEYWORDS

Atmospheric water condensation; Greenhouse microclimate; Water recycling; Water use efficiency; Supplemental irrigation

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

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